

FORMATION OF COMPLEX COMPOUNDS BETWEEN LEAD
NITRATE AND ALKALI NITRATES. PART IX.
THE SYSTEM : $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$

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Experiments with rubidium nitrate-water system, viz., viscosity, conductivity and transport number, indicate that the tendency for the formation of complex compounds is even more than in the case of KNO_3 and NH_4NO_3 system. Three definite complex compounds, viz., (i) $4 \text{RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (ii) $2 \text{RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, and (iii) $\text{RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, analogous to those of potassium and ammonium complexes occur in solution in this system. The formation of complex compounds between lead nitrate and alkali nitrates seems to be conditioned by the order of alkali metals in the Periodic Table, that is, increasing with the atomic number or atomic volume.

In the previous parts of this series (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284, 343; 1949, 30A, 251), we have adduced evidence for the existence of three complex compounds in solution in each of the systems: $\text{KNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, while no such formation could be observed in the systems: $\text{LiNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$. An independent confirmation for the existence of the three complexes in the system: $\text{KNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, has been obtained by Narasimha Murthy (*ibid.*, 1950, 31A, 160). The properties investigated by him were Faraday rotation, refractive index and refractivity dispersion. It was of interest to extend the investigation to other alkali nitrates beyond potassium. In this paper we report our results obtained with the system: $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$. The properties investigated are viscosity, conductivity and transport number. This system has not been investigated before.

EXPERIMENTAL

We had only a limited quantity of rubidium salt in the form of sulphate at our disposal. This was converted into nitrate by carefully treating with an equivalent amount of barium nitrate in solution. The crystals obtained from the filtrate were recrystallised thrice with distilled water and the purity tested by converting a known amount of RbNO_3 into Rb_2SO_4 . It was found to be almost cent per cent pure.

A small flask was blown and calibrated to hold 30 c.c solution. 0.5M-Rubidium nitrate solution (10 c.c.) was pipetted into the flask to which the requisite volume of lead nitrate (0.5M) was added and the mixtures made up to the mark (30 c.c.) by addition of water. In this way 21 solutions were made in which the concentration of rubidium nitrate remained the same (viz. 1/6 M), while that of lead nitrate varied systematically from 0.0M to 1/3 M. The solutions were of the following composition.

Soln. No.	...	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	10
Pb(NO ₃) ₂ added to 10 c.c. RbNO ₃	...	0	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
Soln. No.	...	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
Pb(NO ₃) ₂ added to 10 c.c. RbNO ₃	...	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	14	16

These solutions were stored in steamed reagent bottles (100 c.c. capacity).

Viscosity and Conductivity

The values of viscosity and conductivity are recorded below in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Viscosity.

Temperature = 25 ± 0.05°.

Soln. No.	M/2-Pb (NO ₃) ₂ added to 10 c.c. of M/2-RbNO ₃ soln.	*Viscosity.	Soln. No.	M/2-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ added to 10 c.c. of M/2-RbNO ₃ soln.	*Viscosity.
1	0.0 c.c.	0.9923	12	7.0 c.c.	1.0196
2	1.0	0.9978	13	8.0	1.0210
3	1.5	1.0000	14	9.0	1.0240
4	2.0	1.0030	15	10.0	1.0250
5	2.5	1.0012	16	11.0	1.0350
6	3.0	1.0070	17	12.0	1.0356
7	3.5	1.0070	18	14.0	1.0410
8	4.0	1.0069	19	16.0	1.0470
9	4.5	1.0070	20	18.0	1.0520
10	5.0	1.0069	21	20.0	1.0565
11	6.0	1.0170			

* Viscosity here means relative viscosity i.e. (H₂O=1).

TABLE II

Conductivity.

Cell constant = 28.47.

Temperature = 25 ± 0.05°.

Soln. No.	Conductivity × 10 ⁻³ .	*Resistance.	Soln. No.	Conductivity × 10 ⁻³ .	*Resistance.
1	2.033 mhos	1400 ohms	12	3.462 mhos	823 ohms
2	2.280	1250	13	3.602	791
3	2.438	1173	14	3.8007	750
4	2.583	1100	15	4.1007	695
5	2.758	1037	16	4.102	694
6	2.725	1045	17	4.192	680
7	2.853	998	18	4.512	631
8	3.025	946	19	4.901	581
9	3.241	880	20	5.250	543
10	3.498	816	21	5.566	512
11	3.408	836			

*Refers to the value when the null point was exactly at the centre of the bridge.

When these values were plotted against the concentration of lead nitrate (Figs. 1 and 2), three breaks in the regular curves were obtained at concentrations corresponding to the formation of three compounds :

(a) $4 \text{ RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (b) $2 \text{ RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (c) $\text{RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$

FIG 1

System : $\text{RbNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 Conductivity at 25° .

These curves are exactly analogous to those obtained with the systems containing respectively KNO_3 and NH_4NO_3 (*loc. cit.*). Thus these results taken together with those obtained with LiNO_3 and NaNO_3 indicate that the tendency for complex formation between lead nitrate and alkali nitrates increases as we go beyond potassium and decreases as we proceed below it.

In order to have a quantitatively comparable idea of the behaviour of rubidium with the rest of the alkali nitrates experiments on transport number of Pb ion were also carried out.

Transport number of Pb^{++} ion was determined in $M/24$, $M/48$ and $M/96$ lead nitrate solutions (the choice of the dilution being necessitated by the quantity of RbNO_3 at our disposal). The method employed was the same as described in parts V and VII of this series (*loc. cit.*). After taking measure-

ments with lead nitrate alone, the experiments were repeated with mixtures containing the molecular ratios: $\text{RbNO}_3 : \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 :: (1:1), (1:2)$ and $(4:1)$.

FIG. 2
System : $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.
Viscosity at 25°.

In these solutions the concentration of rubidium nitrate was kept constant (viz., $M/24$), while that of lead nitrate varied according to requirements. The results are tabulated in Tables III and IV.

TABLE III
Transport number of Pb-ion.

System : $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.			System : $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$		
Soln. No.	Conc.	Transport No.	Soln. No.	Conc.	Transport No.
I.	$M/24$	0.4901	I.	$M/24\text{-RbNO}_3 + M/24\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ Ratio (1 : 1)	0.2631
II.	$M/48$	0.4961	II.	$M/24\text{-RbNO}_3 + M/48\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ Ratio (2 : 1)	0.1328
III.	$M/96$	0.4996	III.	$M/24\text{-RbNO}_3 + M/96\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ Ratio (4 : 1)	0.1217

TABLE IV

Percentage change in transport number of Pb-ion in presence of diff. alkali nitrates.

Mol. ratio RNO ₃ : Pb(NO ₃) ₂	(1)* LiNO ₃ .	(2)* NaNO ₃ .	(3)* NH ₄ NO ₃ .	(4)* KNO ₃ .	(5) RbNO ₃ .
(1 : 1)	2.69%	6.40 %	35.3%	38.18%	46.32%
(2 : 1)	5.05	14.32	57.2	60.20	73.23
(4 : 1)	6.87	18.60	68.7	72.20	75.64

Values reproduced from parts V & VII of this series (*loc. cit.*).

The summarised results in Table IV are worthy of close study. It records percentage change effected in the transport number of Pb-ion in the presence of different alkali nitrates.

(a) The percentage change in transport number of Pb-ion in the presence of LiNO₃ is of a very low order *i.e.* (2.69-6.87), indicating the tendency for the formation of complex compounds to be practically nil.

(b) While sodium nitrate affects the transport number of Pb-ion to some extent (6.4-18.6%), showing a slight tendency for the formation of complexes, no stoichiometric relations having been observed.

(c) On the other hand, significant variations in the value of Pb-ion in the presence of KNO₃, NH₄NO₃ and RbNO₃ are obtained. The change effected varies from 35% to 75.6%. This clearly indicates that potassium, ammonium and rubidium nitrates have similar effects, and that the tendency for the formation of complex compounds increases in the same order. Three different orders of magnitude in the values further confirm the presence of three different complexes in each of the three systems.